

pH Dependency of 'Hydration' Water and Iron(III) Complex Formation in Serum Albumin Solution

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Spin-lattice (T1)- and spin-spin (T2) relaxation times of samples of experimental solutions of BSA have been determined in the pH range 7–2. While the reported structural changes are indicated by the increases in T1s, the consequent diminutions of 'hydration' water, associated with the dissolved BSA molecules, are rationalised with the increases of T2s. This gradual loss of individual 'hydration' layers of those BSA molecules leads to the formation of 'molten globule' at pH < 1.5. Any effect of 0.9% NaCl in preserving such 'hydration' water has been investigated. Presence of Na⁺ ions does not favour the development of the characteristic purple colour of the Fe^{III}-BSA complex. A chemical structure of this octahedral arrangement is proposed.

The purpose of this study was to explore BSA's participation, in solution, in acid balance¹, and possible formation of an octahedral Fe^{III}-BSA complex.

Results and discussion

The T1s of different solutions are related with the respective BSA concentrations in the graph (Fig. 1). Those concentrations corresponding to the T2s of the same samples are plotted in the same graph. With the relative increases in the respective protein concentrations, the T2s

were observed to be correspondingly shortened in the experimental dilute solutions. These decreases in the observed T2-readings were related² mostly to the increases in the contents of 'hydration' water in those samples. The effect on T1s of the consequent increases of hydrogen bondings in such samples, was not nearly as strong as it was on T2s. The pHs of the experimental solutions, that were used in the above described T1 and T2 measurements, varied between 5.9 and 7.1.

When 63 mg of BSA was dissolved in 1 ml of water (pH = 7.9), the pH of the solution was measured to be 7.1. This decrease in pH (Table 1) indicated of BSA's participation in acid-base balance. It manifested BSA to be a weak acid¹. The pH of a solution was observed to be higher after BSA was dissolved in the corresponding very dilute acid (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of relaxation time (in ms) vs concentrations of BSA (mg ml⁻¹ of solvent): (O) T1 measurements, and (□) T2 measurements.

Exp.	BSA Lot Number	Solvent description	Solvent pH	Solution pH	pH change
1	98F 0672	Water	7.95	7.1	Decrease
2	98F 0672	0.9% NaCl	6.95	7.1	Increase
3	98F 0672	1.3 μg Fe ^{III} in 0.9% NaCl	1.85	5.15	Increase
4	98F 0672	0.9% NaCl	1.55	4.25	Increase
5	98F 0672 and 30H 0665	2.6 μg Fe ^{III} in 0.9% NaCl	1.55	4.25	Increase

*63 mg BSA was dissolved in 1 ml solvent.

Considering that the presence of Na⁺ ions would be beneficial³ towards the preservation of 'hydration' water and might help in the retention of the globular conformation, a 0.9% NaCl solution was used as the solvent for the experimental solutions. The graphs O and □ in Fig. 2 corresponds to those solutions. The range 'A' denoted by the double-headed arrow at pH = 7.1 in the graph (Fig. 2) is of T1 measurements. At this pH the compact globular form of

Fig. 2. Plots of relaxation time (in ms) vs pH of BSA solutions of the same concentration (63 mg ml^{-1} of solvent): (O) T1s of samples in 0.9% NaCl solutions, (\square) T2s of samples in 0.9% NaCl solutions, (\odot B) T1 of a solution in dilute acid, and (\boxplus C) T2 of the sample in dilute acid.

BSA was supposed to be heart-shaped, since the human serum albumin (HSA) was reported⁴ to be so. As the pH decreased, the TIs of the samples of the respective BSA solutions were observed to increase (O, Fig. 2). While the loosening of the globular form took place within the pH range 7–4.4, continuous structural changes⁵, corresponding primarily to the expansion⁶ of the BSA molecule started. For example, the dramatic increase in TI within the pH range of 4.4 \rightarrow 3.5 was considered to be due to the N (Native) \rightarrow F (Fast moving) transformation in structural⁷ conformation. When the solvent happened to be dilute hydrochloric acid of pH \approx 1.1, the added BSA transformed⁸ into 'molten globule' with lot of bubbles (Table 2).

TABLE 2—'MOLTEN GLOBULE' FORMATION*

Exp.	Solvent description	Solvent pH	Observation	Note
1	Dilute HCl	1.1	Separation of unctuous material with bubbles	Much of that goes into solution after prolonged stirring
2	1.3 μg Fe^{III} ions in 0.9% NaCl	1	As above	As above
3	As above	1	As above	As above

*63 mg BSA (Lot Number . 30H 0665) added to 1 ml solvent under magnetic stirring at room temperature

'molten globule' went into solution, a little translucence and a few specs of solids remained. It was a solution of denatured BSA. Its T1 was distinguishably longer than those described in the graph (Fig. 2). That distinction prevailed in the observed T2s of that sample. The graph (\square ; Fig. 2) related the T2s of BSA solutions with their respective pHs. T2 measurements of different samples at pH \approx 7.1 fell within the range indicated by the double-headed arrow (D) in the graph (Fig. 2).

There has been some controversy during the last 30 years over the nature of change in the contents of 'hydration' water in BSA solutions during the decreasing of their respective pHs. Some investigators considered^{9,10} that to be on the rise. One group¹¹ supported the hypothesis with HSA. A few others, however, stated that the 'hydration' water decreased^{12,13} with the decreasing pH. The observed increases in the measured T2s at lower pHs (\square ; Fig. 2) supported the latter view, that the low pH dehydrated the dissolved proteins¹⁴. As the pH decreased (O and \square ; Fig. 2), H^+ -bound BSA molecules were formed¹⁵. Such H^+ -bindings reduced the content of 'hydration' water in the experimental solution. It also led to the breakdown of the organised physical conformation and gave rise to random coils. This phenomena caused intermolecular associations¹⁴ at pH $<$ 1.5, and ultimately resulted in the formation of the 'molten globule' (Table 2).

The subtle effect of the Na^+ ions on the preservation of the necessary 'hydration' water for the sustenance of the globular conformation may be apparent by comparing the T1 reading at pH = 6.4 from the graph (O; Fig. 2) with those denoted by \odot at B in Fig. 2 of the sample, that did not include any Na^+ ion. In case of the T2-readings of this sample, which were denoted by \boxplus at C in Fig. 2, the difference with that at the graph (\square ; Fig. 2) was distinguishable. This detectable increase in T2 implied of very slight loss of 'hydration' water.

Since the Fe^{III} ions in solution hydrolysed¹⁶ above pH \approx 2 ($-\log K_h$, $pK = 2.17$), the initial pHs of all iron solutions were kept between 1 and 2. In addition to the Fe^{III} ions, some of those solutions also included 0.9% NaCl. The latter was added to explore the effect of the Na^+ ions on the possible enhancement or abatement in the formation of the Fe^{III} -BSA complex. As transferrin, $\alpha\beta_1$ -globulin¹⁷, happened to be the major transport protein of Fe^{III} ions in blood, and not the serum albumin, and that a molecule of BSA did not even have a specific binding site for a Fe^{III} ion, the relative molar proportions of the investigated Fe^{III} ions with respect to the BSA contents, were kept very low (0.019–0.19) in the relevant experiments (graphs O and \square ; Fig. 3). When the concentration of Fe^{III} ions was $1.3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, the measurements of T1 were indicated by Δ and those of T2 by \circ in Fig. 3. For the samples, that

Although, after prolonged stirring, almost all of the

Fig. 3. Plots of \circ and \square correspond respectively to T1 and T2 measurements (in ms) of samples containing a fixed concentration of BSA (63 mg ml^{-1} of solvent) and varying concentrations (mg ml^{-1}) of iron (Δ) T1 at $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron, (\odot) T1 at $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron and BSA (90 mg ml^{-1} of solvent), (\circ) T2 at $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron, (\square) T2 at $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron and BSA (90 mg ml^{-1} of solvent), (\blacktriangle) T1s of iron solutions that included 0.9% NaCl, and (\bullet) T2s of iron solutions that included 0.9% NaCl

included 0.9% NaCl, the plots for T1 were marked by \blacktriangle and those for T2 were denoted \bullet in Fig. 3.

The pHs of the solutions, that contained both BSA and iron were between 4.4 and 6.8. With a fixed amount of BSA in each, the solutions differed in their respective concentrations of iron. The graph \circ (Fig. 3) related the T1s of those samples with their concentrations of iron. Their T2 measurements corresponded to the graph \square (Fig. 3). While the T1 at $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron concentration was shorter (cf. Δ with the graph \circ in Fig. 3), it was not so at the iron concentration of $2.6 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. There the T1 (cf. with graph \circ in Fig. 3) happened to be longer by $\approx E$ ms than that of the sample without any BSA in it. When the concentration of BSA was increased (\odot , Fig. 3) in a sample containing $1.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron, the T1 correspondingly decreased (cf. graph \circ , Fig. 3). It was the same with T2 measurements (\square) (cf. graph \square , Fig. 3).

In the present study, when a Fe^{III} ion got complexed to the favourable site in a BSA molecule, it exhibited a purple colour. If, however, this site corresponded to one of those of the Fe^{III} -citrate-albumin complex¹⁸, a maximum of three such sites were pondered. In any case, Na^+ ions did not

favour the formation of the characteristic colour. Inherent presence of HCO_3^- ions was inferred in the particular BSA product from the observations of many bubbles during the 'molten globule' formation. The development of the purple colour required: (i) pH nearer to 7 (between 6 and 7) and (ii) six oxygen ligands: (a) two from a carbonate, (b) at least two (if not three) from the respective phenolate moieties, and (c) at least one (if not two) from free carboxylate component(s) of the relevant aspartic acid side-chains. Donations of the 12 electrons from the six oxygen ligands to the Fe^{III} moiety in the Fe^{III} -BSA complex conformed to octahedral arrangement.

Experimental

$\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (f.w. 270.3), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (f.w. 404), NaCl (laboratory reagent grade), concentrated hydrochloric acid solution (analytical reagent grade) and deionised water were used. BSA (fraction V) was purchased from Sigma. Since this product was known to include¹⁹ 10% water by weight, the fact was taken into consideration in each calculation of BSA concentration.

A calculated amount of BSA was normally weighed in a 10 (or 25) ml Kontes reaction flask containing a magnetic stirrer. A measured volume of the solvent was added to that under magnetic stirring towards the making of a $\approx 6.3\%$ (w/v) solution. While the magnetic stirring was continued until the solution was clear and transparent, it was not stopped in the alternate method of exploration of making the purple-coloured Fe^{III} -BSA complex in solution. A measured volume of ferric chloride solution was added to the already made (in deionised water), fresh, BSA solution to complete that preparation.

TABLE 3—OCTAHEDRAL Fe^{III} -BSA COMPLEX*				
Exp.	Description of solvent	Fe^{III} in solvent (μg)	Solution pH	Observation
1	Dilute HCl (pH ≈ 2)	0	≈ 6	Colourless
2	FeCl_3 (pH ≈ 2)	1.3	≈ 6	Colour
3	(a) Water (0.95 ml, pH = 7.9) (b) FeCl_3 solution (0.05 ml)	1.3	6.1	Colour

*63 mg BSA dissolved in 1 ml solvent.

Solutions were not degassed²⁰, and it was assumed that the effect of dissolved oxygen on relaxation times was constant from solution to solution. Each sample comprised of 0.5 ml of the experimental solution. It was enclosed in a glass-tube (103×10.25 mm) with a tight-fitting rubber-top before preparing it for the T1 and T2 determinations. This preparation corresponded to attainment of the solution, in the experimental glass-tube, of the probe temperature ($\approx 29^\circ$). The nmr measurements were done at ≈ 13.2 MHz.

The T1 of a sample of deionised water was ≈ 3000 ms and its T2 was ≈ 2000 ms.

A Seimco micropulse magnetic resonance spectrometer (New Kensington, Pa.) was used for all the T1 and T2 measurements. While the T1 determination was modified to saturation recovery of Freeman-Hill method^{21,22}, T2 measurements were according to Meiboom and Gill modification²³ of Carr and Purcell method²⁴.

A Fisher Accumet 900 pH-meter fitted with a calomel electrode was used for most pH measurements. Fisher buffer concentrates for pHs 4 and 7 were diluted, according to the specific directions, in the respective preparations of the reference solutions for the pH-meter adjustments.

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